

Dataset for “Expanding risk predictions of pesticide resistance evolution in arthropod pests with a proxy for selection pressure”

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Preface

This document is a Readme for the work presented in Thia et al. (2023) “Expanding risk predictions of pesticide resistance evolution in arthropod pests with a proxy for selection pressure” *Journal of Pest Science*.

The sections below describe four important directories.

- **00_Functions**, the directory containing important R function scripts.
- **01a_Analyses_Aus**, analyses conducted on Australian pest species.
- **01b_Analyses_USA**, analyses conducted on USA pest species.
- **01c_Analyses_Summarise**, summarization of analyses conducted on both Australian and USA species.

The scripts have been written to accommodate the following directory structure:

```
[Mother dir]/
..... 00_Functions/
..... [X dir]/
..... Data/
..... Results/
..... [Scripts]
```

Let **[X dir]** represent one of the analysis directories, **Data/** and **Results/** are directories nested within **[X dir]**, and **[Scripts]** represents a set of scripts and an R project file. The scripts written are meant to be launched within **[X dir]** via the project file. These scripts read functions stored in **00_Functions**, which shares the same “mother directory”, **[Mother dir]**, as **[X dir]**.

Note, in all tabulated files (e.g., CSV or XLSX), any blank cells should be treated as missing data or no data available.

00_Functions

ENV_my_gg_theme.R

Theme used for ggplot.

FUN_chem_product_sum_by_family.R

Used to sum pesticide product registrations by family.

FUN_custom_colour_hue.R

Custom colour generator.

FUN_do_log.R, FUN_do_log_scale.R, FUN_do_polynomial.R, FUN_do_log_scale_polynomial.R

Perform either a log, scaling, or polynomial transformation, or all three, respectively.

FUN_impute_trait_by_taxon.R

Used to impute traits by their taxonomy.

FUN_logit_marginal_effects.R

Used to estimate marginal effects.

FUN_posterior_risk_scores.R

Used to calculate posterior risk scores from models of resistance status.

FUN_save_ggplot.R

Used to save “ggplot” objects.

FUN_species_name_caps_to_normal.R

Convert species names in all capitals to normal, e.g., “GENUS SPECIES” to “Genus species”.

01a_Analyses_Aus

Data

AusResModel_DATA_00_ALA_Occurrence_Records.csv

Occurrence records of Australian arthropods from the Atlas of Living Australia as of 7 July 2021.

Column name	Data type	Details
Species	Character	Unique species ID
Species Name	Character	Scientific name
Scientific Name Authorship	Character	Taxonomic authority
Taxon Rank	Character	Taxonomic level at which record is assigned
Kingdom	Character	Taxonomic kingdom
Phylum	Character	Taxonomic phylum
Class	Character	Taxonomic class
Order	Character	Taxonomic order
Family	Character	Taxonomic family
Genus	Character	Taxonomic genus
Vernacular Name	Character	Common names

AusResModel_DATA_00_APRD_Aus_Field_Resistances_20210203.csv

Resistance records from the Arthropod Pesticide Resistance Database, as of 3 February 2021.

Column name	Data type	Details
SPECIES	Character	Pest species scientific name
IRAC	Character	The IRAC chemical mode of action: subgroup

AusResModel_DATA_00_APVMA_Filtered_20210426.csv

Australian Pesticides and Veterinary Medicines Authority filtered pesticide product registrations, as of 26 April 2021.

Column name	Data type	Details
No	Integer	Record number
Product	Character	Product description
Status	Character	Product status
Category	Character	Product category
Expiry_date	Date	Product registration expiration
Formulation_type	Character	Product formulation type
Product_type	Character	Product type

Registrant	Character	Product chemical company
Registration_date	Date	Product registration date
Host	Character	Registered crop/use
Pest	Character	Registered pest target, common name
Constituent_name	Character	Chemical active ingredient
Chemical_group	Character	Chemical category
Type	Character	Chemical type
Amount	Numeric	Product formulation amount
Units	Character	Product formulation units
CHEM.GROUP	Character	IRAC chemical mode of action: major group
CHEM.IRAC	Character	IRAC chemical mode of action: subgroup
CHEM.IRAC.GROUP	Character	IRAC chemical mode of action classification
MOA	Integer	IRAC chemical mode of action: major group
Kingdom	Character	Taxonomic kingdom
Phylum	Character	Taxonomic phylum
Class	Character	Taxonomic class
Order	Character	Taxonomic order
Family	Character	Taxonomic family
Genus	Character	Taxonomic genus
Species	Character	Scientific species name

AusResModel_DATA_00_APVMA_Pest_Taxonomy_Working_20210601.xlsx

Assigned taxonomy to pest common names in the APVMA, as of 1 June 2021.

Column name	Data type	Details
Pest	Character	Pest common name
Not_arthropod	Integer	0 (is an arthropod) or 1 (is not an arthropod)
crop_pasture_pest	Integer	0 (not a crop/pasture pest) or 1 (is a crop/pasture pest)
Kingdom	Character	Taxonomic kingdom
Phylum	Character	Taxonomic phylum
Class	Character	Taxonomic class
Order	Character	Taxonomic order
Family	Character	Taxonomic family
Genus	Character	Taxonomic genus
Species	Character	Scientific species name

AusResModel_DATA_00_Aus_Lit_Survey_20220829.xlsx

Literature search of Australian pesticide resistance, as of 29 August 2022.

Column name	Data type	Details
Species	Character	Scientific species name
Author	Character	First author of reference
Year	Character	Published year of reference
Title	Character	Title of reference
Journal	Character	Journal of reference
DOI	Character	DOI of reference
IRAC	Character	IRAC chemical mode of action: subgroup
Mechanism	Character	Character molecular mechanism, if any; “?” where uncharacterised or unresolved
State	Character	Australian state where resistance was documented

AusResModel_DATA_00_Ecological_Traits_20201112.xlsx

Column name	Data type	Details
Ploidy	Character	Ploidy level
Generations_per_year	Character	Generations per year, and notes
Total_number_of_host_plant_families	Character	Number of host plant families
Source	Character	Link to source
Host_plant_family	Character	Names of host plant families

AusResModel_DATA_00_Hardy_Dataset.csv

Data from Hardy et al. (2018) “Does a plant-eating insect's diet govern the evolution of insecticide resistance? Comparative tests of the pre-adaptation hypothesis”.

Column name	Data type	Details
Animal	Character	Species name
Genus	Character	Taxonomic genus
Family	Character	Taxonomic family
Order	Character	Taxonomic order
GPY	Numeric	Generations per year
Host_count	Numeric	Number of host plant families
Poison_count	Numeric	Number of IRAC chemical mode of actions resistant to.
Ploidy	Character	Ploidy level
Docs	Integer	Number of papers on the species.

AusResModel_DATA_01aiv_Trait_Working_Set_20210702.csv

Working set of traits for arthropod pests.

Column name	Data type	Details
Class	Character	Taxonomic class
Order	Character	Taxonomic order
Family	Character	Taxonomic family
Genus	Character	Taxonomic genus
Species	Character	Scientific species name
GPY	Numeric	Generations per year
GPY_Refs	Character	References for generations per year estimates
Phagy	Numeric	Number of host plant families
Phagy_Refs	Character	References for phagy estimates

AusResModel_DATA_01b_APVMA_Products_IRAC.csv

Merged APVMA pesticide product registrations for species.

Column name	Data type	Details
Order	Character	Taxonomic order
Family	Character	Taxonomic family
Genus	Character	Taxonomic genus
Species	Character	Scientific species name
IRAC	Character	IRAC chemical mode of action: subgroups
Products	Integer	Number of APVMA product registrations

AusResModel_DATA_01c_ALA_Matches_Prelim.csv

Initial matches between candidate Australian species list and records of species in the Atlas of Living Australia.

Column name	Data type	Details
Order	Character	Taxonomic order
Family	Character	Taxonomic family
Genus	Character	Taxonomic genus
Species	Character	Scientific species name
ALA	Logical	Was the species recorded in the Atlas of Living Australia?

AusResModel_DATA_01c_ALA_Matches_Prelim_Annotated_20210726.csv

Annotated matches between candidate Australian species list and records of species in the Atlas of Living Australia. Species that could not be matched were manually inspected.

Column name	Data type	Details
Order	Character	Taxonomic order
Family	Character	Taxonomic family

Genus	Character	Taxonomic genus
Species	Character	Scientific species name
ALA	Logical	Was the species recorded in the Atlas of Living Australia?
ALA.check	Logical	Manual re-check to ensure that the species was not missed in the Atlas of Living Australia automated screen.
ALA.url	Character	The URL for the re-checked record in the Atlas of Living Australia.
Other.check	Logical	Was the species an Australian pest based on other sources?
Other.url	Character	The URL for the alternate source of Australian pest status
Is.crop.pest	Integer	“0” is not a crop pest, “1” is a crop pest
Pest	Character	Pest common name

AusResModel_DATA_01d_Traits_Aus.csv

Trait data for those pest species in Thia et al. (2023) “Expanding risk predictions of pesticide resistance evolution in arthropod pests with a proxy for selection pressure”.

Column name	Data type	Details
Order	Character	Taxonomic order
Family	Character	Taxonomic family
Genus	Character	Taxonomic genus
Species	Character	Scientific species name
GPY	Numeric	Generations per year
Phagy	Numeric	The number of host plant families
Study	Character	Pest from Thia et al.
Phagy_Refs	Character	References for phagy estimates
GPY_Refs	Character	References for generations per year estimates
Phagy_impute	Logical	Was the phagy estimate imputed?
GPY_impute	Logical	Was the generations per year estimate imputed?

AusResModel_DATA_01d_Traits_Aus_and_USA.csv

Combined trait data for Australian and American pests. Australian pests are those from the focal study, Thia et al. (2023) “Expanding risk predictions of pesticide resistance evolution in arthropod pests with a proxy for selection pressure”, or Hardy et al. (2018) “Does a plant-eating insect's diet govern the evolution of insecticide resistance? Comparative tests of the pre-adaptation hypothesis”.

Column name	Data type	Details
Order	Character	Taxonomic order
Family	Character	Taxonomic family
Genus	Character	Taxonomic genus
Species	Character	Scientific species name

GPY	Numeric	Generations per year
Phagy	Numeric	The number of host plant families
Study	Character	“Thia” or “Hardy” study
Phagy_Refs	Character	References for phagy estimates
GPY_Refs	Character	References for generations per year estimates
Phagy_impute	Logical	Was the phagy estimate imputed?
GPY_impute	Logical	Was the generations per year estimate imputed?

AusResModel_DATA_02a_Final_Dataset_Imputed.csv

Australian pest working dataset with imputed ecological traits.

Column name	Data type	Details
Order	Character	Taxonomic order
Family	Character	Taxonomic family
Genus	Character	Taxonomic genus
Species	Character	Scientific species name
IRAC	Character	IRAC chemical mode of action: subgroups
Products	Integer	APVMA registered pesticide products
Aus.res	Integer	“0” not resistant in Australia, “1” is resistant in Australia
GPY	Numeric	Generations per year
GPY_impute	Logical	Was the generations per year estimate imputed?
Phagy	Numeric	Number of host plant families
Phagy_impute	Logical	Was the phagy estimate imputed?
Products.log.scale	Numeric	Log-scaled APVMA pesticide product registrations
Phagy.log.scale	Numeric	Log-scaled phagy estimates
GPY.log.scale	Numeric	Log-scaled generations per year estimates
Phage.log.scale.poly1	Numeric	First order polynomial log-scaled phagy estimates
GPY.log.scale.poly1	Numeric	First order polynomial log-scaled generations per year estimates
Phagy.log.scale.poly2	Numeric	Second order polynomial log-scaled phagy estimates
GPY.log.scale.poly2	Numeric	Second order polynomial log-scaled generations per year estimates

AusResModel_DATA_02a_Final_Dataset_Nonimputed.csv

Australian pest working dataset with non-imputed ecological traits.

Column name	Data type	Details
Order	Character	Taxonomic order
Family	Character	Taxonomic family
Genus	Character	Taxonomic genus

Species	Character	Scientific species name
IRAC	Character	IRAC chemical mode of action: subgroups
Products	Integer	APVMA registered pesticide products
Aus.res	Integer	“0” not resistant in Australia, “1” is resistant in Australia
GPY	Numeric	Generations per year
GPY_impute	Logical	Was the generations per year estimate imputed?
Phagy	Numeric	Number of host plant families
Phagy_impute	Logical	Was the phagy estimate imputed?
Products.log.scale	Numeric	Log-scaled APVMA pesticide product registrations
Phagy.log.scale	Numeric	Log-scaled phagy estimates
GPY.log.scale	Numeric	Log-scaled generations per year estimates
Phage.log.scale.poly1	Numeric	First order polynomial log-scaled phagy estimates
GPY.log.scale.poly1	Numeric	First order polynomial log-scaled generations per year estimates
Phagy.log.scale.poly2	Numeric	Second order polynomial log-scaled phagy estimates
GPY.log.scale.poly2	Numeric	Second order polynomial log-scaled generations per year estimates

AusResModel_DATA_02b_CrossVal_Species_Sets.RDS

R list containing 100 training–testing species partitions for cross-validation analyses. Each index contains two vectors:

Vector name	Data type	Details
train	Character	Species used to build a training model
test	Character	Species used to test the model

Results

AusResModel_RESULTS_02a_Bayesian_R2.csv

Bayesian R^2 estimates for tested models of resistance status.

Vector name	Data type	Details
Dataset	Character	“Imputed” of “Non-imputed” ecological trait datasets
Model	Character	“Polynomial”, model fit using all predictors, including the second order polynomials of ecological traits; “Additive”, model fit using additive effects of all predictors; “Ecological”, model fit using only the additive effects of ecological traits; “Ecological^2”, model fit using only the first and second order polynomials of ecological traits; “Operational”, model fit using only pesticide product registrations.
Estimate	Numeric	The Bayesian R^2
Est.Error	Numeric	Standard error of the R^2

Q2.5	Numeric	The 2.5% percentile of R^2
Q97.5	Numeric	The 97.5% percentile of R^2

AusResModel_RESULTS_02a_Imp_Compare_BayesFactor.csv

Comparisons of resistance status models against a null.

Column name	Data type	Details
Model	Character	The model fit.
log_BF	Numeric	Log Bayes factor

AusResModel_RESULTS_02a_Imp_Null.RDS

The null resistance status model for imputed ecological trait datasets; a “brmsfit” object.

AusResModel_RESULTS_02a_Imp_Phagy2GPY2.RDS

The resistance status model fitting just the first and second order polynomials for imputed ecological traits; a “brmsfit” object.

AusResModel_RESULTS_02a_Imp_PhagyGPY.RDS

The resistance status model fitting just the additive effects of imputed ecological traits; a “brmsfit” object.

AusResModel_RESULTS_02a_Imp_Prods.RDS

The resistance status model fitting just the effect of pesticide product registrations; a “brmsfit” object.

AusResModel_RESULTS_02a_Imp_ProdsPhagy2GPY2.RDS

The resistance status model fitting pesticide product registrations and the first and second order polynomials of imputed ecological traits; a “brmsfit” object.

AusResModel_RESULTS_02a_Imp_ProdsPhagyGPY.RDS

The resistance status model fitting the additive effects of pesticide products and imputed ecological traits; a “brmsfit” object.

AusResModel_RESULTS_02a_Logit_Coefficients.csv

Resistance status model partial regression coefficients.

Column name	Data type	Details
Dataset	Character	“Imputed” of “Non-imputed” ecological trait datasets
Model	Character	“Polynomial”, model fit using all predictors, including the second order polynomials of ecological traits; “Additive”, model fit using additive effects of all predictors; “Ecological”, model fit using only the additive effects of ecological traits; “Ecological^2”, model fit using only the first and second order polynomials of ecological traits; “Operational”, model fit using only pesticide product registrations.
Term	Character	Partial regression coefficient name
Estimate	Numeric	Partial regression coefficient estimate
Est.Error	Numeric	Standard error of the partial regression coefficient estimate
Cl.low	Numeric	95% confidence lower limit for the partial regression coefficient estimate
Cl.up	Numeric	95% confidence upper limit for the partial regression coefficient estimate
Rhat	Numeric	Measure of convergence, \hat{R}
Bulk_ESS	Numeric	The bulk effective sample size of the posterior distribution
Tail_ESS	Numeric	The tail effective sample size of the posterior distribution

AusResModel_RESULTS_02a_Logit_Regression_Bayesian.RDS

R list containing all the information from the Bayesian resistance status models. Contains 5 indexes:

List index	Details
imp	Contains a list of the models fit using the imputed ecological trait dataset
noimp	Contains a list of the models fit using the non-imputed ecological trait dataset
R2	Data table of Bayesian R^2
coeffs	Data table of the partial regression coefficients
preds	Data table of predicted values

AusResModel_RESULTS_02a_Noimp_ProdsPhagy2GPY2.RDS

The resistance status model fitting just the first and second order polynomials for non-imputed ecological traits; a “brmsfit” object.

AusResModel_RESULTS_02a_Noimp_PhagyGPY.RDS

The resistance status model fitting the additive effects of pesticide products and non-imputed ecological traits; a “brmsfit” object.

AusResModel_RESULTS_02a_Top_Risks_GGplot.RDS

R “ggplot” object, the predicted risks for the most resistant species.

AusResModel_RESULTS_02b_CrossVal_AUC_Table.csv

Cross-validation analyses for the polynomial and additive resistance status models.

Column name	Data type	Details
Iter	Integer	The iteration number
Dataset	Character	“Imputed” of “Non-imputed” ecological trait datasets
Model	Character	“Polynomial”, model fit using all predictors, including the second order polynomials of ecological traits; “Additive”, model fit using additive effects of all predictors; “Ecological”, model fit using only the additive effects of ecological traits; “Ecological^2”, model fit using only the first and second order polynomials of ecological traits; “Operational”, model fit using only pesticide product registrations.
AUC	Numeric	The “area under the curve” score

AusResModel_RESULTS_02b_CrossVal_Prods.RDS

R list for the cross-validation analyses using the products only resistance status model. Each index contains the predicted risk scores for training species sets:

Column name	Data type	Details
Iter	Integer	The iteration number
Species	Character	Scientific species name
IRAC	Character	IRAC chemical mode of action: subgroups
Aus.res	Integer	“0” not resistant in Australia, “1” is resistant in Australia
y_pred	Numeric	Predicted risk score

AusResModel_RESULTS_02b_CrossVal_ProdsPhagy2GPY2.RDS

R list for the cross-validation analyses using the full polynomial resistance status model, fit with the imputed ecological trait dataset. Each index contains the predicted risk scores for training species sets:

Column name	Data type	Details
Iter	Integer	The iteration number
Species	Character	Scientific species name
IRAC	Character	IRAC chemical mode of action: subgroups
Aus.res	Integer	“0” not resistant in Australia, “1” is resistant in Australia
y_pred	Numeric	Predicted risk score

AusResModel_RESULTS_02b_CrossVal_ProdsPhagyGPY.RDS

R list for the cross-validation analyses using the full additive resistance status model, fit with the imputed ecological trait dataset. Each index contains the predicted risk scores for training species sets:

Column name	Data type	Details
Iter	Integer	The iteration number
Species	Character	Scientific species name
IRAC	Character	IRAC chemical mode of action: subgroups
Aus.res	Integer	“0” not resistant in Australia, “1” is resistant in Australia
y_pred	Numeric	Predicted risk score

AusResModel_RESULTS_03a_Marginal_Effects_GGplot.RDS

R “ggplot” object illustrating marginal effects of the focal predictors in the full polynomial model.

AusResModel_RESULTS_03a_Marginal_Effects_Predict.RDS

R list containing estimates for the marginal effects for the predictor variables, pesticide product registrations, phagy, and generations per year, in the polynomial models, using the imputed ecological trait dataset. Within each of the indexes for the focal predictor, “prods”, “phagy”, and “gpy”, is a data table:

Column name	Data type	Details
Fix	Character	Fixed values for the non-focal predictors. “Median”, non-focal predictors fixed at their medians. “Minimum”, non-focal predictors fixed at their minimums. “98% both”, both non-focal predictors fixed their 98 th percentiles. “98% prods”, product effect fixed at its 98 th percentile and the other non-focal predictor fixed at its minimum. “98% phagy”, phagy effect fixed at its 98 th percentile and the other non-focal predictor fixed at its minimum. “98% voltinism”, generations per year fixed at its 98 th percentile and the other non-focal predictor fixed at its minimum.
Products.log.scale	Numeric	Log-scaled products
Products.log.scale.poly1	Numeric	Log-scaled products first order polynomial
Products.log.scale.poly2	Numeric	Log-scaled products second order polynomial
Products	Numeric	Pesticide product registrations
Phagy.log.scale	Numeric	Log-scaled phagy
Phagy.log.scale.poly1	Numeric	Log-scaled phagy first order polynomial
Phagy.log.scale.poly2	Numeric	Log-scaled phagy second order polynomial
Phagy	Numeric	Number of host plant families
GPY.log.scale	Numeric	Log-scaled generations per year
GPY.log.scale.poly1	Numeric	Log-scaled generations per year first order polynomial
GPY.log.scale.poly2	Numeric	Log-scaled generations per year second order polynomial

GPY	Numeric	Generations per year
b.prod	Numeric	Partial regression coefficient for products
b.phagy1	Numeric	Partial regression coefficient for first order phagy
b.phagy2	Numeric	Partial regression coefficient for second order phagy
b.gpy1	Numeric	Partial regression coefficient for first order generations per year
b.gpy2	Numeric	Partial regression coefficient for second order generations per year
Predict.logit	Numeric	Predicted risk on logit scale
Predict.risk	Numeric	Predicted risk on probability scale

Scripts

AusResModel_CODE_01b_Wrangle_APVMA.R

Script used to parse the APVMA pesticide registration data.

AusResModel_CODE_01c_Atlas_of_Living_Australia.R

Script used to match species to the Atlas of Living Australia presence records.

AusResModel_CODE_01d_Wrangle_Trait_Data.R

Script used to parse and impute trait data.

AusResModel_CODE_02a_Logistic_Regression_Bayesian.R

Script used to format data for logistic regression and combine results from Bayesian analyses.

AusResModel_CODE_02b_Area_Under_Curve.R

Script used to perform cross-validation analyses using receiver-operator characteristics and area under the curve.

AusResModel_CODE_03a_Marginal_Effects_Bayesian.R

Script used to examine the marginal effects of predictors in the polynomial model.

AusResModel_PROJ.Rproj

R project file.

01b_Analyses_USA

Data

USAResModel_DATA_00_APRD_USA_Field_Resistances_20210203.csv

Resistance records from the Arthropod Pesticide Resistance Database, as of 3 February 2021.

Column name	Data type	Details
SPECIES	Character	Pest species scientific name
IRAC	Character	The IRAC chemical mode of action: subgroup

USAResModel_DATA_00_Crossley_Chemical_Map.csv

Chemical mapping of active ingredients from Crossley et al. (2020) “Insect–plant relationships predict the speed of insecticide adaptation” to their IRAC modes of action groups.

Column name	Data type	Details
Active	Character	Chemical active ingredient
MOA	Character	IRAC chemical mode of action: major groups
IRAC	Character	IRAC chemical mode of action: subgroups

USAResModel_DATA_00_Crossley_Dataset.csv

Dataset used in Crossley et al. (2020) “Insect–plant relationships predict the speed of insecticide adaptation”.

Column name	Data type	Details
Start	Integer	Start year of pesticide use
Stop	Integer	Stop year of pesticide use
Delta	Integer	Difference in years
sp	Character	Species name
poison	Character	Chemical active ingredient
chemdist	Numeric	Active ingredient distance to dietary compounds
GENUS	Character	Taxonomic genus
FAMILY	Character	Taxonomic family
ORDER	Character	Taxonomic order
gpy	Numeric	Generations per year
host_count	Numeric	Number of host plant families
poison_count	Integer	Number of chemical groups resistant to
ploidy	Character	“HD”, haplodiploid; “DD”, diploid.
docs	Integer	Number of studies for pest
MoAI2	Character	Chemical class description
closechem	Character	Chemical with similar structure found in diet

USAResModel_DATA_00_EPA_Species_20210623.csv

Environmental Protection Agency pesticide registrations, as of 23 June 2021.

Column name	Data type	Details
Pest	Character	Pest common name
EPA.reg	Character	Product registration number
Active	Character	Chemical active ingredient
MOA	Character	IRAC chemical mode of action: major groups
IRAC	Character	IRAC chemical mode of action: subgroups
Class	Character	Taxonomic class
Order	Character	Taxonomic order
Family	Character	Taxonomic family
Genus	Character	Taxonomic genus
Species	Character	Scientific species name

USAResModel_DATA_00_Hardy_Dataset.csv

Dataset used in Hardy et al. (2018) “Does a plant-eating insect's diet govern the evolution of insecticide resistance? Comparative tests of the pre-adaptation hypothesis”.

Column name	Data type	Details
Animal	Character	Species scientific name
Genus	Character	Taxonomic genus
Family	Character	Taxonomic family
Order	Character	Taxonomic order
GPY	Numeric	Generations per year
Host_count	Numeric	Number of host plant families
Poison_count	Integer	Number of chemical groups resistant to
Ploidy	Character	“HD”, haplodiploid; “DD”, diploid.
Docs	Integer	Number of studies for pest

USAResModel_DATA_01a_Hardy_Matches_Prelim.csv

Initial match of species to those in the Hardy et al. (2018) study to confirm presence of species in USA.

Column name	Data type	Details
Class	Character	Taxonomic class
Order	Character	Taxonomic order
Family	Character	Taxonomic family
Genus	Character	Taxonomic genus

Species	Character	Scientific species name
Hardy	Logical	Was the species present in the Hardy et al. (2018) dataset?

USAResModel_DATA_01a_Hardy_Matches_Prelim_Annotated_20210727.csv

Re-checking those species that could not match those in Hardy et al. (2018).

Column name	Data type	Details
Class	Character	Taxonomic class
Order	Character	Taxonomic order
Family	Character	Taxonomic family
Genus	Character	Taxonomic genus
Species	Character	Scientific species name
Hardy	Logical	Was the species present in the Hardy et al. (2018) dataset?
Other.check	Logical	Was the species a USA pest after manual checking?
Other.url	Character	URL to source.
Is.crop.pest	Integer	“0” is not a crop pest, “1” is a crop pest
Pest	Character	Pest common name

USAResModel_DATA_02a_Final_Dataset_Imputed.csv

USA pest working dataset with imputed ecological traits.

Column name	Data type	Details
Order	Character	Taxonomic order
Family	Character	Taxonomic family
Genus	Character	Taxonomic genus
Species	Character	Scientific species name
IRAC	Character	IRAC chemical mode of action: subgroups
Products	Integer	APVMA registered pesticide products
USA.res	Integer	“0” not resistant in Australia, “1” is resistant in Australia
GPY	Numeric	Generations per year
GPY_impute	Logical	Was the generations per year estimate imputed?
Phagy	Numeric	Number of host plant families
Phagy_impute	Logical	Was the phagy estimate imputed?
Products.log.scale	Numeric	Log-scaled APVMA pesticide product registrations
Phagy.log.scale	Numeric	Log-scaled phagy estimates
GPY.log.scale	Numeric	Log-scaled generations per year estimates
Phage.log.scale.polyI	Numeric	First order polynomial log-scaled phagy estimates
GPY.log.scale.polyI	Numeric	First order polynomial log-scaled generations per year estimates

Phagy.log.scale.poly2	Numeric	Second order polynomial log-scaled phagy estimates
GPY.log.scale.poly2	Numeric	Second order polynomial log-scaled generations per year estimates

USAResModel_DATA_02a_Final_Dataset_Nonimputed.csv

USA pest working dataset with non-imputed ecological traits.

Column name	Data type	Details
Order	Character	Taxonomic order
Family	Character	Taxonomic family
Genus	Character	Taxonomic genus
Species	Character	Scientific species name
IRAC	Character	IRAC chemical mode of action: subgroups
Products	Integer	APVMA registered pesticide products
Aus.res	Integer	“0” not resistant in Australia, “1” is resistant in Australia
GPY	Numeric	Generations per year
GPY_impute	Logical	Was the generations per year estimate imputed?
Phagy	Numeric	Number of host plant families
Phagy_impute	Logical	Was the phagy estimate imputed?
Products.log.scale	Numeric	Log-scaled APVMA pesticide product registrations
Phagy.log.scale	Numeric	Log-scaled phagy estimates
GPY.log.scale	Numeric	Log-scaled generations per year estimates
Phage.log.scale.poly1	Numeric	First order polynomial log-scaled phagy estimates
GPY.log.scale.poly1	Numeric	First order polynomial log-scaled generations per year estimates
Phagy.log.scale.poly2	Numeric	Second order polynomial log-scaled phagy estimates
GPY.log.scale.poly2	Numeric	Second order polynomial log-scaled generations per year estimates

Results

USAResModel_RESULTS_02a_Bayesian_R2.csv

Bayesian R^2 estimates for tested models of resistance status.

Vector name	Data type	Details
Dataset	Character	“Imputed” of “Non-imputed” ecological trait datasets
Model	Character	“Polynomial”, model fit using all predictors, including the second order polynomials of ecological traits; “Additive”, model fit using additive effects of all predictors; “Ecological”, model fit using only the additive effects of ecological traits; “Ecological^2”, model fit using only the first and second

		order polynomials of ecological traits; “Operational”, model fit using only pesticide product registrations.
Estimate	Numeric	The Bayesian R^2
Est.Error	Numeric	Standard error of the R^2
Q2.5	Numeric	The 2.5% percentile of R^2
Q97.5	Numeric	The 97.5% percentile of R^2

USAResModel_RESULTS_02a_Imp_Compare_BayesFactor.csv

Comparisons of resistance status models against a null.

Column name	Data type	Details
Model	Character	The model fit.
log_BF	Numeric	Log Bayes factor

USAResModel_RESULTS_02a_Imp_Null.RDS

The null resistance status model for imputed ecological trait datasets; a “brmsfit” object.

USAResModel_RESULTS_02a_Imp_Phagy2GPY2.RDS

The resistance status model fitting just the first and second order polynomials for imputed ecological traits; a “brmsfit” object.

USAResModel_RESULTS_02a_Imp_PhagyGPY.RDS

The resistance status model fitting just the additive effects of imputed ecological traits; a “brmsfit” object.

USAResModel_RESULTS_02a_Imp_Prods.RDS

The resistance status model fitting just the effect of pesticide product registrations; a “brmsfit” object.

USAResModel_RESULTS_02a_Imp_ProdsPhagy2GPY2.RDS

The resistance status model fitting pesticide product registrations and the first and second order polynomials of imputed ecological traits; a “brmsfit” object.

USAResModel_RESULTS_02a_Imp_ProdsPhagyGPY.RDS

The resistance status model fitting the additive effects of pesticide products and imputed ecological traits; a “brmsfit” object.

USAResModel_RESULTS_02a_Logit_Coefficients.csv

Resistance status model partial regression coefficients.

Column name	Data type	Details
Dataset	Character	“Imputed” of “Non-imputed” ecological trait datasets
Model	Character	“Polynomial”, model fit using all predictors, including the second order polynomials of ecological traits; “Additive”, model fit using additive effects of all predictors; “Ecological”, model fit using only the additive effects of ecological traits; “Ecological^2”, model fit using only the first and second order polynomials of ecological traits; “Operational”, model fit using only pesticide product registrations.
Term	Character	Partial regression coefficient name
Estimate	Numeric	Partial regression coefficient estimate
Est.Error	Numeric	Standard error of the partial regression coefficient estimate
Cl.low	Numeric	95% confidence lower limit for the partial regression coefficient estimate
Cl.up	Numeric	95% confidence upper limit for the partial regression coefficient estimate
Rhat	Numeric	Measure of convergence, \hat{R}
Bulk_ESS	Numeric	The bulk effective sample size of the posterior distribution
Tail_ESS	Numeric	The tail effective sample size of the posterior distribution

USAResModel_RESULTS_02a_Logit_Regression_Bayesian.RDS

R list containing all the information from the Bayesian resistance status models. Contains 5 indexes:

List index	Details
imp	Contains a list of the models fit using the imputed ecological trait dataset
noimp	Contains a list of the models fit using the non-imputed ecological trait dataset
R2	Data table of Bayesian R^2
coeffs	Data table of the partial regression coefficients
preds	Data table of predicted values

USAResModel_RESULTS_02a_Noimp_ProdsPhagy2GPY2.RDS

The resistance status model fitting just the first and second order polynomials for non-imputed ecological traits; a “brmsfit” object.

USAResModel_RESULTS_02a_Noimp_PhagyGPY.RDS

The resistance status model fitting the additive effects of pesticide products and non-imputed ecological traits; a “brmsfit” object.

USAResModel_RESULTS_02a_Top_Risks_GGplot.RDS

R “ggplot” object, the predicted risks for the most resistant species.

USAResModel_RESULTS_02b_CrossVal_AUC_Table.csv

Cross-validation analyses for the polynomial and additive resistance status models.

Column name	Data type	Details
Iter	Integer	The iteration number
Dataset	Character	“Imputed” of “Non-imputed” ecological trait datasets
Model	Character	“Polynomial”, model fit using all predictors, including the second order polynomials of ecological traits; “Additive”, model fit using additive effects of all predictors; “Ecological”, model fit using only the additive effects of ecological traits; “Ecological^2”, model fit using only the first and second order polynomials of ecological traits; “Operational”, model fit using only pesticide product registrations.
AUC	Numeric	The “area under the curve” score

USAResModel_RESULTS_02b_CrossVal_Prods.RDS

R list for the cross-validation analyses using the products only resistance status model. Each index contains the predicted risk scores for training species sets:

Column name	Data type	Details
Iter	Integer	The iteration number
Species	Character	Scientific species name
IRAC	Character	IRAC chemical mode of action: subgroups
Aus.res	Integer	“0” not resistant in Australia, “1” is resistant in Australia
y_pred	Numeric	Predicted risk score

USAResModel_RESULTS_02b_CrossVal_ProdsPhagy2GPY2.RDS

R list for the cross-validation analyses using the full polynomial resistance status model, fit with the imputed ecological trait dataset. Each index contains the predicted risk scores for training species sets:

Column name	Data type	Details
Iter	Integer	The iteration number

Species	Character	Scientific species name
IRAC	Character	IRAC chemical mode of action: subgroups
Aus.res	Integer	“0” not resistant in Australia, “1” is resistant in Australia
y_pred	Numeric	Predicted risk score

USAResModel_RESULTS_02b_CrossVal_ProdsPhagyGPY.RDS

R list for the cross-validation analyses using the full additive resistance status model, fit with the imputed ecological trait dataset. Each index contains the predicted risk scores for training species sets:

Column name	Data type	Details
Iter	Integer	The iteration number
Species	Character	Scientific species name
IRAC	Character	IRAC chemical mode of action: subgroups
Aus.res	Integer	“0” not resistant in Australia, “1” is resistant in Australia
y_pred	Numeric	Predicted risk score

USAResModel_RESULTS_03a_Marginal_Effects_GGplot.RDS

R “ggplot” object illustrating marginal effects of the focal predictors in the full polynomial model.

USAResModel_RESULTS_03a_Marginal_Effects_Predict.RDS

R list containing estimates for the marginal effects for the predictor variables, pesticide product registrations, phagy, and generations per year, in the polynomial models, using the imputed ecological trait dataset. Within each of the indexes for the focal predictor, “prods”, “phagy”, and “gpy”, is a data table:

Column name	Data type	Details
Fix	Character	Fixed values for the non-focal predictors. “Median”, non-focal predictors fixed at their medians. “Minimum”, non-focal predictors fixed at their minimums. “98% both”, both non-focal predictors fixed their 98 th percentiles. “98% prods”, product effect fixed at its 98 th percentile and the other non-focal predictor fixed at its minimum. “98% phagy”, phagy effect fixed at its 98 th percentile and the other non-focal predictor fixed at its minimum. “98% voltinism”, generations per year fixed at its 98 th percentile and the other non-focal predictor fixed at its minimum.
Products.log.scale	Numeric	Log-scaled products
Products.log.scale.poly1	Numeric	Log-scaled products first order polynomial
Products.log.scale.poly2	Numeric	Log-scaled products second order polynomial
Products	Numeric	Pesticide product registrations
Phagy.log.scale	Numeric	Log-scaled phagy
Phagy.log.scale.poly1	Numeric	Log-scaled phagy first order polynomial

Phagy.log.scale.poly2	Numeric	Log-scaled phagy second order polynomial
Phagy	Numeric	Number of host plant families
GPY.log.scale	Numeric	Log-scaled generations per year
GPY.log.scale.poly1	Numeric	Log-scaled generations per year first order polynomial
GPY.log.scale.poly2	Numeric	Log-scaled generations per year second order polynomial
GPY	Numeric	Generations per year
b.prod	Numeric	Partial regression coefficient for products
b.phagy1	Numeric	Partial regression coefficient for first order phagy
b.phagy2	Numeric	Partial regression coefficient for second order phagy
b.gpy1	Numeric	Partial regression coefficient for first order generations per year
b.gpy2	Numeric	Partial regression coefficient for second order generations per year
Predict.logit	Numeric	Predicted risk on logit scale
Predict.risk	Numeric	Predicted risk on probability scale

Scripts

USAResModel_CODE_01a_USA_Species_Check.R

Script used to match species to the Hardy et al. (2018) dataset.

USAResModel_CODE_02a_Logistic_Regression_Bayesian.R

Script used to format data for logistic regression and combine results from Bayesian analyses.

USAResModel_CODE_02b_Area_Under_Curve.R

Script used to perform cross-validation analyses using receiver-operator characteristics and area under the curve.

USAResModel_CODE_03a_Marginal_Effects_Bayesian.R

Script used to examine the marginal effects of predictors in the polynomial model.

USAResModel_PROJ.Rproj

R project file.

01c_Analyses_Summarise

Data

irac_moa_details.csv

Molecular targets for different pesticide chemical mode of action groups.

Column name	Data type	Details
TARGET	Character	Molecular target
IRAC	Character	IRAC chemical mode of action: major groups
CHEMICAL.CLASS	Character	Chemical class

Results

irac_moa_details.csv

Molecular targets for different pesticide chemical mode of action groups, with all matched active ingredients observed in this study assigned.

Column name	Data type	Details
TARGET	Character	Molecular target
IRAC	Character	IRAC chemical mode of action: major groups
CHEMICAL.CLASS	Character	Chemical class
ACTIVE	Character	String of active ingredients, each separated with a comma

Scripts

Summarise_CODE_01a_Combined_Country_Figures.R

Script used to make figures that summarise the results from both the Australian and USA datasets and analyses.

Summarise_CODE_02_IRAC_Actives.R

Script used to gather all IRAC active ingredients observed in this study and match to their chemical modes of action.

Summarise_PROJ.Rproj

R project file.